

Manganese Dioxide Oxidation of Oximes

J. S. SANDHU* & SURESH MOHAN**

Department of Chemistry Punjabi University, Patiala

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Large number of functional groups are known to undergo oxidations with activated manganese dioxide¹. These classes of compounds include allylic alcohols², allylic amines³, hydrazones amino nitriles⁴ and imines⁵. The present report describes finding on the oxidation of oximes with manganese dioxide.

The oximes used here were obtained according to already well known methods. Activated manganese dioxide was prepared from manganese sulfate dihydrate and potassium permanganate⁶.

The oxime Ia (0.01 mole) was refluxed for several hours with large excess of (0.04 mole) of manganese dioxide in dry benzene. The removal of inorganic material and solvent gave a white product which was crystallised from ethanol to give compound IIa, m.p. 115° in 54% yield the elemental analysis, (Found C 70.2%, H 4.1%, N 11.5%, requires C 70.8%, H 4.4%, N 11.0%) I.R. and mass spectrum supported the assigned structure IIa for the oxidised compound. The mass spectrum showed M⁺ at m/e 238 along with other prominent peaks at m/e 222 (M-16), m/e 208 (M-30) m/e 178, m/e 175, m/e, 163, m/e 152, m/e 139, m/e 103, m/e 76.

Ia	X = H	IIa	X = H	m.p. 115°
Ib	X = <i>p</i> -Cl	IIb	X = Cl	m.p. 145°
Ic	X = <i>o</i> -Cl	IIc	X = <i>o</i> -Cl	m.p. 131°

The compound IIa was further confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample.

Present address * Regional Research Laboratories, Hyderabad.

** Guru Nanak University, Amritsar.

The Mass spectrum of compound IIa further deserves a comment as to the presence of peak at m/e 178 (basepeak) is indicative of phenanthrene ion system. Its further fragmentation pattern is consistent with that of phenanthrene systems.

When other oximes with substitution p -Cl and o -Cl were used the reaction was faster and was complete in 48 hrs. However in case of oximes with electron releasing groups the oximes were recovered unchanged. This further elaborates the role of electronic factors in these manganese dioxide-oxidations.

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